

A GIS-Based Approach to Enhance Safety and Accessibility of Shared Mobility Services

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Abstract. The implementation of shared mobility services within cities plays an influential key role in enhancing sustainability by optimizing the use of transport resources, reducing the number of private vehicles, and mitigating traffic congestion and carbon emissions, thus contributing to a greener and more eco-friendly urban environment. Nonetheless, the full potential of shared mobility services may be hindered by inadequate walkability of the locations for pick-up and drop-off points. High accident risks can deter users from accessing service pick-up points, thereby constraining the adoption of these sustainable transport solutions.

In this regard, the paper presents a comprehensive methodological approach based on spatial analysis using Geographic Information Systems (GIS) that examines various levels of data to analyse the interplay between accidents and accessibility. This method allows for a deeper understanding of how urban design influences safety and accessibility in shared mobility. By integrating multiple layers of spatial data, i.e. accident hotspots and topology and infrastructural features of the pedestrian transport network, the study allows a twofold “BS-ScOREs – BikeSharing - Safety and accessibility Outcome Rating Evaluations” for an overall qualitative and quantitative assessment within the buffers around service pick-up points and highlight punctual criticalities. The method was applied to a case study, considering the bikesharing stations in Palermo (Italy). A well-designed pedestrian-friendly environment complements these shared services, enabling convenient access to transport hubs and enhancing the overall accessibility and usability of sustainable mobility alternatives within urban areas. Research outcomes can support establishing safe and well-planned pedestrian environments at these locations and, along with implementing road safety initiatives, can enhance confidence and encourage broader engagement with shared mobility services. Further research will focus on applying the method to other points of interest (e.g. carsharing

stations; schools), encompassing additional characteristics linked to walkability and conducting in-field surveys to validate the findings.

Keywords. Accident analysis; Walkability; Bikesharing; GIS; Shared mobility.

1 Introduction

As a result of rapid urbanization and the associated growing challenges posed by traffic congestion, air pollution and constrained availability of transport alternatives, shared mobility services have emerged as transformative solutions reshaping urban transport landscapes around the world [1, 2]. These innovative services, characterised by accessibility, cost-effectiveness and environmental sustainability, represent a paradigm shift for people moving within cities, promoting sustainable mobility [3].

Shared mobility encompasses different transport modes, e.g. ridesharing, carsharing, bikesharing and scooter-sharing [4]. Bikesharing enables users with the flexibility to rent bicycles for short-term use, usually for riding within urban areas. Besides constituting an alternative to the ownership of private car, this shared transport system can also complement existing public transport systems by offering first- and last-mile connection for users [5, 6].

Dock-based bikesharing systems are characterised by designed docking stations where users can pick up and drop off bicycles using cards or smartphone applications. These stations are strategically located throughout the city, e.g. usually close to transit hubs, shopping centers and residential areas, enabling integration with other transport modes. Dockless bikesharing systems, on the other hand, operate without fixed docking stations. Instead, bicycles are equipped with GPS technology and can be located and unlocked via smartphone apps. Users have the option of picking up and dropping off bicycles at any location within a specific service area, offering greater convenience and straightforwardness for short trips. The choice of implementing dock-based or dockless bikesharing models depends on several factors, including urban density, user preferences and the regulatory framework [7-9]. While dock-based systems offer greater predictability and reliability in bicycle availability, dockless systems provide greater flexibility and coverage, particularly in larger urban environments.

Focusing on dock-based bikesharing systems, some relevant aspects to be considered regarding bikesharing stations are [10-13]:

- the strategic location of stations along transport network to maximize accessibility and service use. Stations should be easily accessible from main points of interest, e.g. public transport terminals, offices, shops and residential areas;
- safe and direct access to the stations, paying attention to the design and maintenance of road infrastructure, as well as providing dedicated access links (e.g. via cycle paths or designed routes);
- connecting bikesharing stations to existing cycle path networks or, if necessary, extending cycle paths to access stations ensuring cyclists to move safely and easily from the station to their final destination and vice versa;

- clear signage of road infrastructure and guidance for cyclists to the nearest bikesharing stations. This may comprise road signs, directional signs and cycle route maps indicating the location of the nearest stations;
- the availability of safe and designed bicycle parking spaces along the road infrastructure close to bikesharing stations in order to encourage cyclists to use the service, as they can easily and safely park the bicycle when they have completed the trip;
- the maintenance and cleanliness of areas around bikesharing stations, including the maintenance of cycle paths, removal of obstacles and cleaning of bicycle parking areas. A well-maintained environment while considering all these factors can contribute to the improvement of the overall experience of cyclists and encourage citizens to use bikesharing.

Among these factors, a dichotomy can be detected in real contexts between what is more important for the operator (i.e. accessibility) and what is essential for the user (i.e. safety). Hence, the aim of the work is to propose a methodological approach based on spatial analysis using Geographic Information Systems (GIS), in order to perform a comprehensive assessment of the areas around bikesharing stations. Specifically, through the integration of multiple layers of spatial data, it has been possible to calculate two 'BS-ScOREs - BikeSharing - Safety and accessibility Outcome Rating Evaluations' based on the number of accidents and topology of transport network, respectively, to identify hotspots within the accessible pedestrian network and perform an assessment of its infrastructural features.

The paper is organized as follows: the introduction discussed the role of sharing mobility, focusing on bikesharing, and aspects related to stations and access road infrastructures within urban areas; then, Section 2 proposes the methodological approach, explaining the formulations related to the calculation of the two BS-ScOREs; Section 3 illustrates the case study, describing the territorial framework and information about the accident data used; Section 4 presents the research findings through graphical and numerical evidence; finally Section 5 concludes the work and highlights future insights.

2 Methodological approach

This section presents the comprehensive methodological approach proposed in this study, characterized by the calculation of the two BS-ScOREs, based on the number of accidents and the topology of the transport network, as described in the previous section. Figure 1 shows the procedural steps of the methodology.

Fig. 1. Methodological framework

More specifically, the attributes considered for the calculation of each BS-ScOREs will be outlined, with the mathematical formulations used for their quantification.

2.1 Accessibility score

In order to measure the pedestrian accessibility of bikesharing stations, a well-known indicator in the literature has been applied. The Pedestrian Catchment Area ratio, or Ped-shed ratio, developed by [14], is a ratio calculated with the following Equation 1:

$$\text{Accessibility BS - ScORE}_{B_{\varepsilon}(x_i)}^i = PCA_{B_{\varepsilon}(x_i)}^i = \frac{A_{network}^i}{A_{ideal}^i} \quad (1)$$

where:

- i is the analyzed bikesharing station located at x_i ;
- $B_{\varepsilon}(x_i)$ is a complete neighborhood (i.e. buffer) centered at x_i with radius ε ;
- $A_{network}^i$ is the network-defined pedestrian service area calculated using network-based distances for the generic bikesharing station i ;
- A_{ideal}^i is the ideal pedestrian service area calculated using Euclidean distances for the generic bikesharing station i .

PCA ratio measures how well the road network covers the area around a specific key destination. Values of the ratio close to 1 indicate extremely walkable areas, while a score less than 0.30 would reflect an inaccessible walking environment. Although there has not been enough research to determine an optimal PCA score, it is suggested that a minimum score of 0.5-0.6 is a useful threshold [14].

PCA ratio can be assessed through a GIS-based analysis: the ideal pedestrian service area can be calculated by performing a Buffering operation, setting as the radius of the buffer the average distance pedestrians are willing to walk to reach the

nearest bikesharing station; the network-defined pedestrian service area can be identified using the Service Area tool, considering the road network imported by OpenStreetMap to calculate the network-distances.

2.2 Safety score

There are several attributes to be considered when assessing the safety of pedestrian road infrastructure, for instance [15-18]:

- Pedestrian accident rates: Number of accidents involving pedestrians in relation to the entire population or number of pedestrians;
- Pedestrian fatality rates: Number of deaths involving pedestrians' accidents compared to the entire population or number of pedestrians.
- Pedestrian injury rates: Number of injured pedestrians involved in accidents compared to the entire population or number of pedestrians;
- Pedestrian accident severity index: A measure of the degree of severity of pedestrian accidents, considering the number of fatalities and the severity of injuries.
- Pedestrian hotspots: Identification of high-risk areas for pedestrians, e.g. intersections, crosswalks, and high-traffic areas.
- Quality of pedestrian infrastructure: Assessment of the maintenance conditions at sidewalks, crosswalks, pedestrian signage, presence of lighting, etc.
- Pedestrian compliance rates: Percentage of pedestrians complying with crossing rules, using pedestrian crossings, etc.
- Supervision and enforcement rates: Measure of the effectiveness of monitoring and enforcement measures, e.g. presence of pedestrian traffic lights, raised crossings, etc.
- Levels of education and awareness: Measure of the level of pedestrian education and public awareness of pedestrian hazards and safe crossing practices.
- Economic effects of pedestrian accidents: Economic costs resulting from pedestrian accidents, including property damage, medical expenses, productivity gains, etc.

Based on this overview, considering the number of accidents related to a defined time interval and which occurred within the catchment area of bikesharing stations, the following safety-related BS-SCORE has been calculated, according to the following equation (Equation 2):

$$\text{Safety BS - SCORE}_{B_\varepsilon(x_i)}^i = \frac{\sum_{k=1}^n A_k^i}{\max_i A_k^i} \quad (2)$$

where:

- i is the analyzed bikesharing station located at x_i ;
- $B_\varepsilon(x_i)$ is a complete neighborhood (i.e. buffer) centered at x_i with radius ε ;
- n represents the total number of points (i.e. accidents) within the buffer;

- $\sum_{k=1}^n A_k^i$ is the number of accidents within the buffer for the generic bikesharing station i ;
- $\max_i A_k^i$ is the maximum number of accidents recorded within a buffer.

This index can vary between 0 and 1. Values closer to 1 indicate the occurrence of a high number of accidents and therefore a critical situation around the considered bikesharing station.

3 Case study

3.1 Territorial framework

In the city of Palermo (Italy), a dock-based public bikesharing service, called “AmiGO”, is currently operated by the municipally owned company AMAT s.p.a., which is the main public transport operator in the city, managing the urban bus service and the tram network. The service, previously called “BiciPa”, was launched by AMAT in 2016 thanks to the co-financing from the Italian Ministry of the Environment. In December 2019, the service was integrated with carsharing, so it is possible to use both services with a single subscription, as well as using the same smartphone application and the same payment gateway. The integration of carsharing and bikesharing in a single platform is a unique case in Italy.

In December 2020, the service had a fleet of 417 traditional bicycles, of which 298 available for users and 119 in the depot. However, following widespread vandalism of bicycles and docking stations, as well as the launch of e-scooter sharing and dockless bikesharing services in the aftermath of the COVID-19 pandemic, which led users towards the emerging shared transport solutions, the service counts a smaller fleet available to users (less than 50 bicycles).

Users can pick up and drop off bicycles at the 42 bikesharing stations located throughout the municipality. Bicycles can be unlocked via a smartphone application. The cost of an annual subscription, including also the carsharing service, is 25€ and the rental charge is determined by the time of use (i.e. the rate increases every half an hour of use). The first 30 minutes of rental are free, which makes the service attractive for short-distance trips. The 30-minute free charge is applied to the next rental if at least three hours have passed in between.

3.2 Data on the use of bikesharing in Palermo

In order to understand how bikesharing is used in Palermo, operator data from 2019 was obtained and analysed. The number of subscribers to the service in 2019 was 2,601. The average rental distance was around 2.5 km and the average rental lasted 20 minutes. The total trips made in 2019 were 34,672. On average, 95 daily trips were made with 93% of rentals lasting less than half an hour. Seventy-two per cent of rentals produced mileages between 1 and 3 km.

The months in which the most trips were made were October and May, while a lower than average number of trips was made in January and December (cold

months), and August (hot month); the latter represents the month characterized by the least use. The average number of daily rentals for weekends was only 36 rentals, compared to an average number of daily rentals for weekdays equal to 121.

Furthermore, only 11% of total trips were made on weekends. Bikesharing is therefore, most likely used by people who travel every day for work reasons. This is also confirmed by the time slots in which the bikesharing service was most used: they are the morning rush hour (8am-10am), the one between 1 pm and 2 pm and the one between 5pm and 6pm.

Considering the identification numbers listed in Table 1 (see Section 4.1), the most used bikesharing stations as origins of the trips were station 26-Piazza Unità d'Italia (2,733 trips), 4-Piazza G. Cesare (2,673), 18-Piazza A. Gentili (2,672), 12-Piazza F. Crispi (2,225) and 1-Piazza Castelnuovo (2,138). The bikesharing stations least used as origins were station 41-Sferracavallo-Via Torretta (1 ride), 40-Mondello – Piazza Mondello (4), 39-Mondello Viale Regina Elena (31), 36-Mondello – Piazza Caboto (39) and 42-Villa Niscredi (51).

The bikesharing stations that were most used as destinations were station 26-Piazza Unità d'Italia (2,826 rides), 18-Piazza A. Gentili (2,699), 4-Piazza G. Cesare (2,680), 12-Piazza F. Crispi (2,394) and 1-Piazza Castelnuovo (2,159). The bikesharing stations least used as destinations were station 41-Sferracavallo-Via Torretta (1 ride), 40-Mondello – Piazza Mondello (13), 39-Mondello Viale Regina Elena (52), 42-Villa Niscredi (55) and 36-Mondello – Piazza Caboto (56).

As can be seen, the most used stations are the same both as origin of trips and as destination. The same can be said for the less used ones. The least used bikesharing stations in 2019 were those located in the northern part of the city. This means that bikesharing is used more in the city center rather than in the suburban areas.

The most popular routes taken by users of the shared bike service were Piazza G. Cesare – Piazzale Unità (466 trips), Piazzale Unità – Piazzale G. Cesare (435) and Piazzale Unità – Piazza A. Gentili (367). This means that mostly short trips are made in the city center and that bikesharing is not used to connect the center to the suburbs.

3.3 Accident data

The data about accidents involving pedestrians in the city of Palermo have been collected by consulting the Municipal Police database. This database contains all the statistical information that the city police officers collect every time an accident involving a pedestrian occurs. The data refer to a period of eight years, from 1st January 2015 to 31st December 2022. During this period, 1,999 accidents occurred within the municipal boundaries. Using the information available in the Municipal Police database, it has been possible to classify accidents by severity (i.e. fatal injuries; severe injuries requiring hospitalization; minor injuries; injuries with unknown prognosis) and also by the dynamics of the event.

Considering 500 meters as walkable distance and performing a GIS spatial analysis based on the geoprocessing tool 'Intersection', the accidents in the 500m-buffers around the bikesharing stations have been identified (see Figure 2). During the analysis period, 1,204 accidents occurred within the buffers of the bikesharing

stations, 27 of which were fatal accidents and 42 resulted in life-threatening injuries requiring hospitalization. The highest number of accidents (200) occurred in 2017, while the lowest number (102) occurred during 2021, due to the consequences of the restrictions imposed by the Italian government to control the COVID-19 diffusion.

Most of the accidents occurred during the morning peak hours from 9am to 12pm (23.5%), from 12pm to 3pm (17.7%), and during evening peak hours from 6pm to 9pm (20.4%), when people go to or come back from work and most of the office and shops are open, while very few accidents happened during nighttime (9.4% from 9pm to 6am) or weekends (only 226 accidents out of 1,204). 914 accidents out of 1,204 (76%) were reported as collisions between pedestrians and vehicles running along the road, while 43 were collisions with vehicles reversing and 35 were collisions with vehicles that were rear-ended; 37 were reported as pedestrian falls due to road degradation; finally, 175 accidents had an unclear dynamic.

Considering the collisions with running vehicles, the main causes of accidents were attributed to the pedestrian not using pedestrian crossing (281 times), the driver not respecting the pedestrian's right of way at crossings (271 times), and the driver not moderating the speed (123 times). As can be observed from Figure 2, the bikesharing stations in whose service area the greatest number of accidents occurred are those in the city center; the suburban areas, which are affected by lower pedestrian flows, also had a low number of accidents involving pedestrians. The accidents mainly occurred in urban neighborhood roads (type E road according to the Italian road classification) rather than in local roads (type F).

Fig. 2. Bikesharing stations with their identification number, color-coded by number of accidents that occurred in their theoretical pedestrian service area.

4 Results ad discussions

In this section, the results are presented and discussed to provide valuable insights into the accessibility and safety of the areas surrounding the bikesharing stations in Palermo. First the findings of the accessibility analysis are presented through a map and numerical indicators. Next, the number of accidents is graphically evaluated, identifying the most critical spots. Finally, the infrastructural characteristics of the transport network are examined according to the indicators that can be found in [19-22], thus presenting the overall assessment of the pedestrian environment around the bikesharing stations.

4.1 Accessibility and safety evaluation

First, the results of the accessibility evaluation highlighted that 24 out of 42 stations (i.e. 57%) have a PCA ratio above 0.5 and 31% above 0.6. This indicates that the location of Palermo's bikesharing service stations has been conducted considering their accessibility, indeed almost all the stations have good pedestrian accessibility. Figure 3 shows bikesharing stations color-coded by PCA ratio.

Fig. 3. Bikesharing stations with their identification number color-coded by PCA ratio.

It can be observed from the graphical representation and from the numerical quantification reported in Table 1 that few bikesharing stations are characterized by slightly low PCA values: in particular, this occurs (i) for stations located near

maritime neighborhoods (e.g. stations 36, 39, 40 and 41) and (ii) near the University Campus (e.g. stations 33, 35 and 38). In the first case, PCA values are characterized by a reduced pedestrian area calculated using network-based distances compared to the ideal pedestrian area calculated using Euclidean distances, since part of the buffer includes a portion of the sea; in the second case, the University Campus represents a particular point of interest, for which there are specific entry and exit points, limiting the extension of access road infrastructures. Table 1 also summarizes the results obtained by the safety evaluation and the scores for each bikesharing station.

By classifying the stations based on the number of accidents occurring in their catchment area, the first ten stations (Figure 4) have accessibility above average (average PCA ratio = 0.51) (see Figure 5). Nevertheless, they account for 35.6% of the accidents that occurred in the catchment areas of bikesharing stations (429 accidents out of 1,204).

Fig. 4. Top ten bikesharing stations by number of accidents.

Table 1. Accessibility and safety Scores

Station id	Name	Acc. BS-ScORE	Saf. BS-ScORE
1	Piazza Castelnuovo	0.62	1.00
2	Piazzale Ungheria	0.61	0.90
3	Via Cavour	0.65	0.76
4	Piazza G. Cesare	0.65	0.71
5	Piazza Ignazio Florio	0.59	0.66

6	Piazzetta Due Palme	0.58	0.65
7	Via Volturno	0.66	0.62
8	Piazza Cassa di Risparmio	0.66	0.54
9	Largo Cavaliere del S. Sepolcro	0.65	0.54
10	Cassaro Alto	0.65	0.53
11	Viale Praga	0.53	0.50
12	Piazza F. Crispi	0.61	0.46
13	Piazza Magione	0.53	0.46
14	Via M. di Villabianca	0.62	0.45
15	Via Emilia	0.54	0.45
16	Piazza Don Bosco	0.63	0.43
17	Piazza De Gasperi	0.65	0.41
18	Piazza A. Gentili	0.55	0.38
19	Piazza XIII Vittime	0.54	0.38
20	Via Parlatore	0.35	0.38
21	Piazza Marina	0.57	0.37
22	Piazza della Vittoria	0.45	0.37
23	Via Terrasanta	0.46	0.34
24	Viale Francia	0.52	0.33
25	Stazione Notarbartolo - Via Gen. Di Maria	0.43	0.32
26	Piazza Unità d'Italia	0.50	0.30
27	Via Archirafi	0.37	0.27
28	Piazza Giachery	0.54	0.26
29	Via Aquileia	0.49	0.25
30	Piazzale J. Lennon	0.44	0.24
31	Via Pindemonte	0.46	0.22
32	Via Autonomia Siciliana	0.48	0.17
33	Polo Didattico Università	0.41	0.15
34	Piazza Acquasanta	0.42	0.11
35	Università Edificio 17	0.09	0.11
36	Mondello - Piazza Caboto	0.61	0.10
37	Parco della Salute	0.31	0.10
38	Università - Facoltà di Lettere	0.38	0.08
39	Mondello Viale Regina Elena	0.42	0.07
40	Mondello-Piazza Mondello	0.36	0.07
41	Sferracavallo-Via Torretta	0.28	0.04
42	Villa Niscemi	0.48	0.02

Fig. 5. Trends Accessibility and Safety SCOREs

Although there are bikesharing stations having locations characterized by good accessibility, they are also affected by a high number of accidents, which could influence and negatively impact the use of the bikesharing service. Thus, in accordance with previous literature looking at safety aspects of the pedestrian environment, and considering the top ten bikesharing stations by number of accidents, few hotspots have been qualitatively analysed examining in detail the criticalities attributed to the infrastructure, that could have led to a high number of accidents.

The following factors have been identified as influencing the safety of the pedestrian environment: lighting, speed and flow of vehicular traffic, presence of barriers on the pavement to protect pedestrians, presence of driveways, traffic lights at the pedestrian crossing, visibility of the pedestrian crossing (presence of obstacles), maintenance of crosswalk markings, absence of the pedestrian crossing at the intersection, and crossing length.

The first analyzed hotspot is Via Roma (Figure 6) which falls in the service areas of all the top 10 bikesharing stations except for number 7. Via Roma is a neighborhood street characterized by high vehicle flows and speeds of 50 km/h. This road is now two-way, but in the reference period of the accident analysis, it was characterized by a one-way segment in the northern part and a two-way segment in the southern part. There is poor maintenance of the pedestrian crossings, and, in several intersections, there are no pedestrian crossings. This frequently induces pedestrians to cross irregularly in order not to lengthen their path, following their desire lines (i.e. the shortest paths). Furthermore, in Figure 6 it can be noted that the road intersects a pedestrian area. However, there are no barriers to direct pedestrians to the nearest crosswalk. The lighting is hindered by the trees, making it pedestrian unfriendly. The intersections are mostly without traffic lights.

Fig. 6. Via Roma

The second hotspot is Via Libertà, which is a neighborhood street characterized by high vehicle flows and speeds of 50 km/h, having two one-way service roads (one per direction) running parallel to the main one-way road. Most of the accidents occurred in the service roads (Figure 7), having a small width but high traffic volumes. In many intersections there are no pedestrian crossings, and the visibility of crossing pedestrians is limited by obstacles such as legally or illegally parked cars.

Fig. 7. Via Libertà

The third and the fourth hotspots analyzed here are Piazza Castelnuovo and Piazza Sturzo (Figure 8). These two squares are characterized by large roads with high traffic volumes and speed over 50 km/h, resulting in excessive crossing lengths that expose pedestrians to greater risk of accidents. Moreover, a bus stop located in Piazza Castelnuovo does not have pedestrian crossings nearby.

Fig. 8. Piazza Castelnuovo and Piazza Sturzo

5 Conclusions

As cities continue to struggle with the complexities of urban mobility, shared mobility has emerged as a key contributor to sustainable transport, offering a pathway to more equitable, efficient, and environmentally friendly urban transport systems.

Walking is the main mode of transport to access shared mobility services. In this perspective, pedestrian accessibility and safety of the pedestrian environment are two crucial aspects to be considered by operators and local authorities promoting shared mobility. In this study, focusing on dock-based bikesharing service within the city of Palermo, a methodology was developed involving the calculation of two indices to assess accessibility and safety around bikesharing stations in urban areas. These indices have been calculated using a combination of spatial analysis techniques and accident data, providing further considerations on the critical infrastructural features impacting the environments surrounding the stations.

The case study showed that the bikesharing service operator in Palermo has located most of the stations in accessible areas; however, some of these areas are characterized by a high number of accidents involving pedestrians. A qualitative analysis using some indicators developed in previous studies found that most of the accidents occurred on roads having negative indicators, validating their accuracy in measuring the safety of the pedestrian environment.

To conclude, the relationship between bikesharing stations and pedestrian environment is crucial in ensuring the accessibility, convenience, and safety of bikesharing services for urban dwellers. Well-designed road infrastructure and effective collaboration between service providers and local authorities can help in maximizing the use of bikesharing systems and their benefits within communities.

Further studies will focus on applying the method to other points of interest (e.g. carsharing stations; schools), encompassing additional characteristics linked to walkability and conducting in-field surveys to validate the findings.

Acknowledgments. This research was funded by the European Union—FESR or FSE, National Operational Programme (NOP) on Research and Innovation 2014-2020—DM 1062/2021. This research was also funded by the European Union - Next-Generation EU – National Sustainable Mobility Center CN00000023, Italian Ministry of University and Research Decree n. 1033 -17/06/2022, Spoke 9, CUP B73C22000760001. The work of Vincenza Torrisi is funded by the European Union – Next-Generation EU, through the MUR-PNRR project SAMOTHRACE (ECS00000022).

Disclosure of Interests. The authors have no competing interests to declare that are relevant to the content of this article.

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